

Impact Of Coronavirus (Covid-19) Pandemic Lockdown On Students' Academic Activities In Federal College Of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State: Implication For Counselling

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on infrastructure and social behaviour of students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State. Four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated and test at 0.05 alpha level of significance to guide the study. This study adopted survey research design. Stratified random sampling technique was used to obtain a total of three schools out of Nineteen schools in the college with a total population of 600 students and 200 student were drawn from the total population. The instrument used for data collection was structured questionnaire with two sections and 15 items in relation to impact of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on infrastructure and social behaviour of students. The instrument was correlated using four-point likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics was used to analyze the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The mean benchmark of 2.50 was accepted while any mean below 2.50 were rejected. The study revealed that there was high impact of corona virus (covid-19) pandemic on the social behaviour of students, high impact on teacher-student relationship of the students and high impact on the study approach of students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku. Based on the findings, it was recommended amongst others that education authorities should step up adequate supervisions of learning activities and teaching transactions in the schools and implement the use of e-learning facilities in all schools so that in times of crisis teaching and learning can still be carried out effectively. Teachers/lecturers in colleges should attend conferences, seminars and workshops to acquire new knowledge on how to increase skills and competencies in utilising electronic and online teaching and learning technologies and counselling should also extend expertise to meet up lost grounds

Key words: Coronavirus Pandemic, Lockdown, Students, Academic activities, Counselling

Introduction

The Oxford dictionary defines coronavirus disease otherwise called (COVID-19) as a contagious disease caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome called coronavirus 2. Coronavirus pandemic was found to belong to the coronaviridian family in the nidovirales order. Corona represents crown-like spikes on the outer surface of the virus; thus it was named as a coronavirus. COVID-19 first emerged in December, 2019 when a cluster of patients with pneumonia of unknown cause was identified in the province of Wuhan province in China, and subsequently was declared in March 11, 2020 by the World Health Organisation as pandemic disease. The disease has neither approved medicine nor vaccine for treatment and has made governments and medical scholars to search for drastic measures to combat the continued spread of the pandemic but all to no avail. Since cure is not possible, measures of control became necessary. The application of non-pharmaceutical strategies such as quarantining, isolation and public health education became options of control.

The coronavirus disease pandemic has caused a sudden significant increase in hospitalisation for pneumonia with multi-organ diseases. The infection may be symptomatic or it may cause a wide spectrum of symptoms such as mild symptoms of upper respiratory tract infection and life-threatening sepsis (WHO, 2019).

As at July, 2020, SARS-CoV2 had affected more than 200 countries of the world, resulting in more than 10 million identified cases with 508,000 confirmed deaths. Genomic analysis revealed that COVID-19 is phylogenetically related to severe acute respiratory syndrome-like (SARS) bat-like viruses, therefore bats were suggested to be the possible primary source and spread to human. However, the immediate source of origin and transfer to human is difficult to ascertain and therefore unknown. All is based on assumption (Hui, 2020).

Concept of coronavirus (COVID-19)

Coronavirus referred to as (COVID-19), implies ‘CO’ for corona, ‘VI’ for virus, ‘D’ for disease and ‘19’ for 2019. It is a disease which emanates from animals such as bats, cats, camels and monkey. It causes severe respiratory syndrome and common cold. COVID-19 affects people of any ages with symptoms as fever, cough, tiredness, headache, loss of taste and smell, sore throat, congestions in nose, vomiting, diarrhea, persistent chest pain among others. The disease is said to be commonly found in animals but rarely found in humans (Baytiyeh, 2020).

Origin of COVID-19

Health experts assume that the strain of Coronavirus originated from bat or any other mammal with long tail (pangolin). The first noticeable transmission to man took place in Wuhan, a city in Hubei province in China. The first recorded case of coronavirus was found in animal market in China where there was a serious possible transmission from human to human (WHO, 2019). These viruses live in animals but do not infect them. The belief was that the viruses are likely to change or undergo mutation and transfer to other species. Sometimes, the virus may transfer from animal species to infect human beings. This way, Hui (2020) explains the pandemic infected human for the first time in China market where food, fish and live animals were sold. Scientists and other researchers are still investigating to know the exact mode of spread. However, evidences exist that the virus can be transmitted directly from person to person through close contacts (Onyije, Gbobo & Onyije, 2021; Hui, 2020).

Coronavirus pandemic created serious impacts on different facets of life including the school system. A school is a landed facility or building where learners receive educational orientation. In his idea about school, Barret (2020) notes that school is a place for training, education, teaching or disciplining of an individual for social development. Further, the author notes that a school is any institution in which instructions are given in a particular discipline in a particular way. In the same school system, achievement in teaching, research, information are made for the benefits of the learners (Okebukola 2014). Despite these great expected achievements and benefits of the school, the outbreak of the coronavirus (COVID-19) made a remarkable damage to it which also involved Federal College of Education (Tech), Omoku.

The theory of fear, depression and anxiety which hinge on vague unpleasant emotional state with qualities of apprehension, dread, distress and uneasiness are synonymous with this study (Bandura, 1977 in Ikenyiri, 2019). There was jittering, fear and anxiety among the students who were infected and those who were yet infected by the virus who are potential victims.

In their study on the effect of coronavirus pandemic on secondary school students in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni local government area in Rivers State, Onyije, Gbobo & Onyije (2021), carried out an empirical study using twelve public secondary schools. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design of pre-test, post-test and control design. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 to guide the study. The sample of the study was 42 senior secondary school students, the instrument used for data collection was questionnaire titled 'impact of coronavirus pandemic on secondary school students'. Two experts in measurement and Evaluation validated the instrument. A test-retest reliability of 0.71 was obtained. The result indicated that there was no significant difference between impact of coronavirus and learning processes of secondary school students in the said local government. It came to lime light that the pandemic really had a negative impact on the learning of the students as many of them were not used to individualistic learning at home. The e-learning platforms adopted by some homes posed serious challenges to the majority of the students because of the limited access to the internet and lack of the technical know-how to handle the devices by most students (Wang, 2020).

Statement of Problem

During the pandemic, schools were on total lockdown, weeds and reptiles overtook the school environment and some structures in the school became dilapidated because of lack of care and maintenance. Still as a result of the pandemic, many examinations were postponed such as the West Africa Senior School Certificate (WASSC), National Examination Council (NECO), National Technical Examination and semester examinations of tertiary institutions of which Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku was included. All intra and extra curricula activities in the school were halted. The cordial interpersonal relationships of the students with their lecturers were denied them.

During the same pandemic, students saw it as opportunity to engage in antisocial behaviours such as armed robbery, rape, prostitutions, kidnapping and more involved in cultism. Most students used the opportunity of school lock down to cause violence in their communities and pains on their parents. Others became drug addicts with Indian hemp, cocaine and other similar drugs. A good number of the students embarked on cyber crimes to make quick money. Since learning was abandoned, there was no access to teaching practice supervisors of the students including Industrial Training programme. This study therefore seeks to investigate the impact of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on Federal College of Education (Technical), students in Rivers State.

Research Question

The following research questions were posed to guide the study thus:

1. What is the impact of Coronavirus pandemic on the social behaviour of the students at home?
2. What is the impact of Coronavirus pandemic on teacher-student relationship?
3. To what extent does Coronavirus pandemic affect the study approach of the students in the College?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance to guide the study thus:

1. There is no significant difference between impacts of Coronavirus pandemic and social behaviour of the students at home.
2. There is no significant difference between impacts of Coronavirus pandemic and teacher-student relationship in the College.
3. There is no significant difference between the impacts of Coronavirus pandemic and the study approach of the students in the school.

Methodology

This study adopted survey research design which aimed at collecting and identifying information on certain variables and their relationship to one another.

The population of this study consisted of 300 NCE II students drawn from three schools within the college, which included, School of Business Education, School of Vocational Education and School of Arts and Social Sciences. The researchers used stratified random sampling techniques to select 200 students drawn from the three schools in the college thus: School of Business Education=85 students, School of Vocational Education=60 and School of Arts and social sciences=55, total was 200 students. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire with two sections, A & B. Section A contained the respondents' biodata information of age, department, and sex, while section B contained 20-items in relation to impact of coronavirus pandemic on students. The instrument was correlated using four-point Likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE), with points as 4, 3, 2, 1, respectively. The instrument was developed by the researchers and sent to two experts one from Measurement and Evaluation and another from Sociology of Education specialists. They were requested to ascertain the suitability of the items, clarity of language, and construct appropriateness of the items to the study. Thereafter, their corrections and observations were integrated into the final draft of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained by administering copies of the instrument to schools outside the sample study. After two weeks interval, the items on the instrument were readjusted and re-administered to the same set of students and test-retest statistics was used to correlate the scores and it yielded a co-efficient value of 0.63. This was adjudged adequate to sustain the study on impact of coronavirus pandemic on students in Federal College of Education (Tech), Omoku, Rivers State. The questionnaire was personally administered by the researchers to the respondents and retrieved directly from

the same respondents after few days and that method ensured 100% collection. Mean and standard deviation were employed to answer the research questions while IBM SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science), version 22 was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level of significance. Any derived mean from the response options that was equal to the bench mark of 2.50 was remarked “agreed” and any mean below 2.50 was remarked “not agreed”.

Results

Research Question One: What is the impact of Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on the social behaviours of the students while at home?

Table 1: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis results of impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Social Behaviour of Students during the lockdown.

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark on the extent
2.	Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic is one of the causes of negative social behaviour students assumed during the long holidays.	200	3.37	.513	High
3.	Kidnapping, killing, smoking, cultism, rape etc amongst others are some of the negative social behaviours.	200	3.44	.623	High
4.	Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic has impact on student's social behaviour during the long holidays created by the pandemic.	200	3.91	.326	High
Valid N (list wise) / Grand mean		200	3.57		

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 1 shows the summary of descriptive statistics results of impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the social behaviours of students in FCE (T), Omoku, in Rivers State. The mean value ranges from 3.37 to 3.91. All the items in the instrument had mean values (3.37, 3.44 and 3.91) above the bench mark of 2.50 and a corresponding standard deviation of .513, .623, and .326 respectively. A grand mean of 3.57, implies that the impact of coronavirus pandemic on the social behaviour of students was very high.

Results for Test of Hypothesis 1

H₀1: There is no significant difference between impact of COVID-19 pandemic and social behaviour of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

Table 2: Pearson Correlations of the Impact COVID-19 Pandemic and the Social Behaviour of Students.

			Students' social behavior	Causes of negative social behavior	Kidnapping, killing, smoking, cultism, rape etc.
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation		1	.028	.058*
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.693	.412
	N		200	200	200
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation		.028*	1	-.080
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.693		.257
	N		200	200	200
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation		.058	-.080	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.412	.257	
	N		200	200	200

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (two-tailed).

Table 8 shows the correlation coefficients r (.028, .058, -.080) and 2-tailed test of significance values (.693, .257, .412). The null hypothesis is rejected implying that there is significant relationship between impact of COVID-19 pandemic and the social behaviours of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku during the lockdown.

Research Question Two: What is the impact of Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on the teacher-students' relationship in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku?

Table 3: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis results of impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on the Teacher-Student Relationship during the pandemic.

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark on the extent
5	Students' poor performance after the pandemic is as a result of lack of teacher-students relationship in terms of learning during the pandemic.	200	3.38	.545	High
6	Teacher-students relationship was affected because of lack in communication and learning activities during the long holidays created by the pandemic.	200	3.51	.743	High
7	Teacher-students relationship was greatly affected during the coronavirus pandemic.	200	3.74	.506	High
Valid N (listwise) / Grand mean		200	3.54		

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 2 shows the summary of descriptive statistics results of impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the teacher-students' relationship of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between impact of COVID-19 pandemic and the teacher-student relationship of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

Table 4: Pearson Correlations of the Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic and the teacher-student relationship of the students.

			Teacher-students' relationship	Lack of relationship in terms of learning	Lack of communication between teachers and learners
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation		1	.221*	.187*
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.002	.008
	N		200	200	200
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation		.221*	1	.276*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002		.000
	N		200	200	200
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation		.187*	.276*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.008	.000	
	N		200	200	200

*Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (two-tailed).

Table 4 shows the correlation coefficients r (.221, .187, .276) and 2-tailed test of significance values (.002, .008, .000). The null hypothesis was rejected implying that there was significant difference between impact of COVID-19 pandemic and the teacher-student relationship in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

The instrument had mean values of (3.38, 3.51 and 3.74) above the bench mark of 2.50 and a corresponding standard deviation of .545, .743, and .506 respectively. A grand mean of 3.54, implying that impact of Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on the teacher-students' relationship in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku was high.

Research Question Three: To what extent does Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic affect the study approach of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku?

Table 5: Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis results of the extent COVID-19 Pandemic affect the study approach of the students.

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Remark on the extent
11	Study approach of students was affected as students developed poor study habit and could no longer read and study their books at home during the pandemic.	200	3.31	.572	High
12	Study activities in the college stopped during the pandemic causing the students to perform less in their study as some resorted to online approach due to the long holidays created by the pandemic.	200	3.40	.764	High
13	Study approach of students was affected because they could no longer access any learning activities in the school due to the pandemic.	200	3.66	.645	High
Valid N (listwise) / Grand mean		200	3.46		

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 7 shows the summary of descriptive statistics results of impact of COVID-19 pandemic on study approach of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, in Rivers State. The mean value ranges from 3.31 to 3.66. All the items in the instrument had mean values (3.31, 3.40 and 3.66) above the bench mark of 2.50 and a corresponding standard deviation of .572, .764, and .645 respectively. A grand mean of 3.46, implying that Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic affect the study approach of the students in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku.

H₀4: There is no significant difference between the impacts of COVID-19 pandemic and the study approach of students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

Table 6: Pearson Correlations of the Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic and the Study Approach of Students in Federal College Education (T), Omoku.

		Study approach affected – no longer access any learning activities	Study approach affected – developed poor study habit	Study approach affected – study activities stopped
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation	1	.169	.240
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.017	.001
	N	200	200	200
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation	.169	1	.132
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017		.062
	N	200	200	200
Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic	Pearson Correlation	.240	.132	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.062	
	N	200	200	200

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 8 shows the correlation coefficients r (.169, .240, .132) and 2-tailed test of significance values (.017, .001, .062). The null hypothesis is rejected implying that there is significant difference between impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the study approach of students in Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku.

Discussion of Major Findings

The findings of this study were organised and discussed under the specific purposes and arranged according to the subheading of the study as follow:

Impacts of Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on the social behaviours of the students.

There was high sorrowful impact of coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic on the social behaviour of students while at home during the lock down as shown in the result on test of hypothesis one. The respondents accepted that students assumed some negative social behaviours during the lockdown; such as

smoking, increase in cultism, rape, vandalism and generally there was break down of law and order under the period. This finding was in agreement with the findings of Baytiyeh (2020) who opined that delinquency was high among the students during the long holidays created by the pandemic. Okebukola (2014) also supported that despite the great achievements and benefits by the school, the outbreak of the coronavirus (COVID-19) made a remarkable damage in social behaviours of the students in the College.

Impact of Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic on teacher-students' relationship

There was also a high impact of coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic on teacher-student relationship. The students could not reach their lecturers for academic help in areas such as project supervision, teaching practice programme, Industrial Training supervision. The same group of students were denied, extra-curricular activities like games and sporting activities. Other issues students could not discuss with their guidance counsellors within the period of the pandemic include their personal-social cases such as marriage, dating and other similar matters. These findings were also in agreement with the finding obtained by Jegede, (2020) who opined that lecturers-student relationship did not exist during the lockdown which affected the academic work of the students such as assignments. In support of this, Onyije, et al (2021) accepted that students found it difficult to access and discuss academic issues with their lecturers and counsellors.

Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic on study approach of students in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku.

The result of hypothesis four of this study revealed that students developed poor study habit and could no longer give interest to study. The students no longer access any learning activities due to the pandemic. The e-learning platforms adopted by some homes posed serious problems to many of the students because of lack of the technical know-how of the students to access internet online. (Wang, 2020) and (UNESCO, 2020) were in subscribed that students could no longer engage themselves in any meaningful academic activities. Those who tried could not create any impact because they were not used to online learning and those who knew it were disrupted by lack of electricity power.

Counselling Implication

The mode of spread of the coronavirus disease and its awareness must be tackled by the guidance counsellor through mounting of effective campaign strategy on the spread of the pandemic on human. Counsellors should extend the responsibility to organise aggressive orientation service programmes on protocols such as spread and control of the pandemic among the students. The counsellors require the need to routinely train on how to create behaviour change in the students such as the correct application of face mask, social and physical distancing, practice of good hygiene like washing of hands, refusal to touch the nose, eye, mouth and other sensitive components of the body carelessly. Counselling is expected to eradicate the emotional, psychological and physiological trauma experienced by the victims by improving their low-self concept and self-esteem, fear, anxiety and elements of neuroticism that may exist in the victims which are capable of eaten deep in them as they return to school. The label of stigma by their fellow students and the general public place on them basic source of further frustration, negative poor self-concept, feelings of inadequacies, low motivation, dependency and a sense of futility among the infected students. Counsellors and medical experts are expected to handle each coronavirus case of the victims with extreme care and confidentiality to avoid exposing them to the general public who may worsen their emotional conditions by stigmatizing them.

Conclusion

This study found that there sorrowful high impact of coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic on the social behaviour of students while at home. The students engaged in anti-social behaviours such as kidnapping, stealing and robbery, cybercrimes, prostitutions and promiscuity, rape and other such obnoxious and indecent behaviours. There was negative impact of the disease on teacher-student relationship in the college which denied the students a lot of services including counselling. Many activities and programmes were inaccessible by the Students and were separated from their lecturers and academic work in the school suffered setbacks.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should improve and step-up standard of education by implementing the use of e-learning facilities in all schools so that in times of crisis or pandemic, teaching and learning can still be carried out effectively while the students are at home.
2. Counselling programmes should be encouraged highly in the school as the students return back to resume classes. The purpose of the counselling activities is to sort out students who were attacked by the pandemic to relax their emotions and trauma experienced during the period.
3. The school authority should endeavour to adjust the academic calendar and supervise the lecturers closely to meet up the lost grounds.

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